

APPENDIX C – INTERVIEW SCRIPT FOR THE FOCUS GROUPS

Investigating the Online Recruitment and Selection Journey of Novice Software Engineers: Anti-patterns and Recommendations

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Research Objective: To identify a set of antipatterns and recommended practices suggested by recruiters for entry-level professionals in the online Recruitment and Selection (R&S) processes for positions in the field of Software Engineering.

01. What is an antipattern?

Antipatterns are typical responses to recurring problems that are usually ineffective and can be highly counterproductive.

02. What is a recommendation?

A recommendation is the action and consequence of recommending (suggesting something, giving advice). Therefore, a recommendation can be a suggestion related to a certain issue.

03. Evaluated Phases:

a. Application Collection:

Any action directly linked to acquiring information about the candidate. This can occur through the receipt of resumes (CVs and/or R&S software), digital platforms (such as LinkedIn), social networks, and third-party referrals.

b. Behavioral Assessment:

Methods that verify, measure, and assess essential aspects of candidates' behavior. In this phase, qualities and defects, strengths and weaknesses, virtues, and vulnerabilities are observed and considered, classifying and categorizing each candidate.

c. Technical Assessment:

The entire process by which evidence of an individual's performance and knowledge regarding required professional competencies can be collected. This can occur through technical interviews and tests/exams.

04. Guiding Questions on Application Collection:

- a. What are the most critical and recurring antipatterns you face during the online Application Collection phase?
- b. Considering these antipatterns, what recommendations would you suggest for candidates to avoid them in this phase of the process?

05. Guiding Questions on Behavioral and Technical Assessments:

a. Behavioral Assessment:

- i. What are the most critical and recurring antipatterns you face in the online Behavioral Assessment phase?
- ii. Given these antipatterns, what recommendations would you suggest for candidates to avoid them in this phase of the process?

b. Technical Assessment:

- i. What are the most critical and recurring antipatterns you face in the online Technical Assessment phase?
- ii. Given these antipatterns, what recommendations would you suggest for candidates to avoid them in this phase of the process?

06. General Questions:

- a. Are issues related to the candidate's market vision and knowledge of the company they applied to evaluated?
- b. During your assessment, what aspects draw your attention regarding the demonstration of the candidate's soft skills?
- c. What is your opinion on the need (or lack thereof) for public project portfolios (on GitHub, for example)? How often do you evaluate such items?
- d. What is your view on the influence of the candidate's digital presence (blogs, YouTube channel, social media profile, etc.) in the R&S process?

- e. What would be your main recommendations regarding the use of digital platforms for the exposure of resumes/experience (such as LinkedIn and GitHub)?